

SOUNDSCAPE PREFERENCE RATING USING SEMANTIC DIFFERENTIAL PAIRS AND THE SELF-ASSESSMENT MANIKIN

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the findings of a soundscape preference rating study designed to assess the suitability of the self-assessment manikin (SAM) for measuring an individual's subjective response to a soundscape. The use of semantic differential (SD) pairs for this purpose is a well established method, but one that can be quite time consuming and not immediately intuitive to the non-expert. The SAM is a questionnaire tool designed for the measurement of emotional response to a given stimulus. Whilst the SAM has seen some limited use in a soundscape context, it has yet to be explicitly compared to the established SD pairs methodology. This study makes use of B-format soundscape recordings, made at a range of locations including rural, suburban, and urban environments, presented to test participants over a 16-speaker surround-sound listening setup. Each recording was rated using the SAM and set of SD pairs chosen following a survey of previous studies. Results show the SAM to be a suitable method for the evaluation of soundscapes that is more intuitive and less time-consuming than SD pairs.

1. INTRODUCTION

Environmental noise has been increasingly recognised as a form of pollution equally important as more traditional pollutants [1]. In order to understand how the negative effects of noise pollution arise, a method extending beyond noise level measurement is required. One such method is auralisation where a measured or simulated soundscape can be presented in a lab environment, and subjective responses to that soundscape can then be measured [2].

The established method for gathering these subjective responses is the use of SD pairs [3] to rate soundscapes in terms of multiple scales. This method can be time consuming, due to the cumbersomeness of measuring perhaps 18 or more ratings for each stimulus in a given test. It can also be non-intuitive for non-experts where specific terms are used, and relies on an understanding of the terms used which requires translation and validation for use in multiple languages [4]. The SAM consists of only three scales

presented in pictorial form and was generated in an attempt to design a preference rating tool free from these problems.

It is hypothesised that a comparison of soundscape preference rating results between a set of SD pairs and the SAM will show the SAM to be a directly comparable and equally useful tool for the analysis of subjective soundscape experience.

This paper first considers the test methodology, including the decisions made in data collection and the subjective assessment methods used. The results from this experiment are shown, with the SAM and SD pair results compared using correlational analysis. The ratings of the recorded soundscapes are also presented in terms of Russell's circumplex model of affect [5]. This paper ends with a concluding section showing the above hypothesis to be supported by the collected evidence. This section also considers avenues for further research.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Data Collection

During Summer 2015 data were collected from 8 locations around the north of England covering a wide range of environments from rural to suburban and urban. At each location audio-visual recordings were made using a 4-channel Soundfield surround-sound microphone and 6-GoPro cameras mounted on a cube allowing for the capture of spherical images. The visual data were collected for use in further experiments. The aim when choosing the recording locations was to cover as wide a range of sound sources, noise levels, and visual features as possible.

2.1.1 Sound Sources

In order to select a set of recording locations covering as wide a range of soundscapes as possible, previously identified categories of soundscapes and their components sound sources had to be considered. In a significant quantity of soundscape research [6–11] three main groups of sounds are identified:

- **Natural sounds:** These include animal sounds (bird song is an oft-cited example), and other naturally occurring environmental sound.
- **Human sounds:** Any sounds that are representative of human presence/activity that do not also represent

industrial activity. Such sounds include footsteps, speech, coughing, laughter etc.

- **Industrial sounds:** Mechanical sounds, such as traffic noise, activity on a building site, or aeroplane noise.

The purpose of covering such a wide range of sources was to ultimately generate a set of stimuli that will elicit a wide range of emotional responses. Generally speaking, natural sounds are the most preferred, human sounds are given a neutral rating, and mechanical/industrial sounds are disliked [10].

2.1.2 Recording Duration

Several minutes of material were recorded at each location, from which two 30-second long clips were extracted. Table 1 contains details of the sound sources present in the two 30-second long clips chosen to represent each recording location. Where here the clips are numbered as ‘1’ and ‘2’ for each location, when referred to more generally they have each been given a number between 1 and 16, determined by the order of the locations. For example, the clips numbered 3 and 4 are respectively the 1st and 2nd clips recorded at location 2.

A survey of previous literature showed the duration of recordings used for soundscape reproduction to vary considerably. Whilst Harriet made use of 7-minute long soundscape representations [8] constructed artificially from recorded material, other studies typically use shorter recordings (especially those presenting visual and aural stimuli simultaneously). For example both Anderson et al. [10] and Viollon et al. [7] used 20-second long recordings. Pheasant et al. have used 32-second long recordings [12, 13], and both Watts and Pheasant and Gifford and Ng make use of recordings lasting 1-minute [11, 14]. Axelsson’s work as part of the Sound Cities project used binaural recording of 46-seconds in length, presented with a set of six still images of the recording site [15]. Rummukainen et al. used even shorter recordings only 15-seconds in length [16].

The majority of these have considered visual stimulus alongside aural information, and most audio only studies have made use of soundwalks [3, 8, 17–19] which are naturally longer in duration. Work by Fröhlich et al [20] has previously confirmed the ecological validity [21] of short (c. 10-second long) video clips in quality of experience studies. Following this survey it was decided that 30-second long clips would be suitably long to present an immersive and ecological valid scenario to test participants without making the test too long.

2.2 Subjective Assessment

This section covers the methods of subjective assessment to be used in rating the recorded soundscapes. The purpose of this experiment was to assess the suitability of the Self-Assessment Manikin for soundscape preference rating by comparing results gathered from the use of the SAM with those obtained from ratings made with a set of semantic differential pairs.

2.2.1 Semantic Descriptors

The use of SD pairs is a method originally developed by Osgood to indirectly measure a person’s interpretation of the meaning of certain words [22]. The method involves the use of a set of bipolar (typically 7-point [23]) descriptor scales, for example ‘Weak - Strong’, allowing the user to rate a given stimulus. Factor analysis can then be performed on the results to determine underlying patterns connecting the various descriptor pairs [4].

The use of Semantic Differential (SD) pairs for the assessment of soundscape quality is well established [3, 8, 18, 23–27], and includes the use of both connotative and denotative scales. Denotative scales relate to the acoustic or psychoacoustic properties of the soundscape, whereas connotative scales measure the emotional meaning [26]. Table 2 shows the set of SD pairs used in this experiment. It was generated from a survey of previous studies, and the table shows where each of the SD pairs selected have been used in other studies.

Figure 1. The Self-Assessment Manikin (SAM) as used in this experiment, after [4].

2.2.2 The Self-Assessment Manikin

The Self-Assessment Manikin (SAM) is a method for measuring emotional responses developed by Bradley and Lang in 1994 [4]. It was developed from factor analysis of a set of SD pairs rating both aural [28, 29] and visual stimuli [30] (using both the International Affective Digital Sounds database, or IADS, and the International Affective Picture System, or IAPS). The three factors developed for rating emotional response to a given stimuli are:

- **Valence:** How positive or negative the emotion is, ranging from unpleasant feelings to pleasant feelings of happiness.
- **Arousal:** How excited or apathetic the emotion is, ranging from sleepiness or boredom to frantic excitement
- **Dominance:** The extent to which the emotion makes the subject feel they are in control of the situation,

Site	Clip 1 Sound Sources	Clip 2 Sound Sources
1. Dalby Forest	Birdsong, owl hoots, wind	Birdsong, goose honking, insects, aeroplane noise
2. Dalby Forest Lake	Wind, birdsong, insects, single car	Wind, birdsong, insects, water splashing
3. Hole of Horcum	Birdsong, traffic, bleating	Birdsong, traffic, conversation
4. Fox & Rabbit Inn	Traffic, car door closing	Traffic, car starting, footsteps
5. Smiddy Hill	Car starting, car door closing, traffic	Traffic, birdsong
6. Albion Street	Busker performance, footsteps, conversation, distant traffic	Workmen, footsteps, conversation
7. Park Row	Traffic, buses, wind, 'flute' playing	See clip 1 details
8. Park Square	Conversation, traffic, birdsong, shouting	Workmen, conversation, birdsong, traffic

Table 1. Details of the sound sources present in the two 30 second long clips used for each location.

#	Semantic Differential Pair	Harriet [8]	Kang [3]	Davies [24]	Viollon [25]
1	Quiet-Noisy	×	×	×	×
2	Comfort-Discomfort	×	×	×	×
3	Unique-Common (Interesting-Boring)	×	(×)	(×)	(×)
4	Monotonous-Variied (Varied-Simple) [Static-Changing]	×	(×)	(×)	[×]
5	Pleasant-Unpleasant	×	×	×	
6	Harmonious-Disharmonious (Gentle-Harsh)	×	(×)	(×)	
7	Soft-Rough (Soft-Hard)	×	(×)	(×)	
8	Natural-Artificial (Rural-Urban)		×	×	(×)
9	Social-Unsocial (Friendly-Unfriendly)		×	×	(×)
10	Calming-Agitating		×	×	×
11	Meaningful-Meaningless (Informative-Uninformative)		×	(×)	

Table 2. Details of the SD pairs used in this study, with their use in previous studies indicated.

ranging from not at all in control to totally in control.

These results were then used by Bradley and Lang to create the SAM itself as a set of pictorial representations of the three identified factors. The version of the SAM used in this experiment is shown in Figure 1.

The SAM has been used a select number of times for soundscape analysis, recently by Watts and Pheasant [11], and combined with concurrent physiological measures by Hume and Ahtamad [31]. However, a direct comparison of SD pair ratings with SAM results has not been conducted. Other studies have investigated the use of Russell's circumplex affect model [5] to study urban environments. Hull and Harvey found a relationship between the physical characteristics of suburban parks and affective states: tree density, and the presence of undergrowth and pathways [32], while Hanyu found that green, open, and well-kept spaces are related to positive valence, but that the presence of 'disorder elements' (vehicles, wires) is related to negative affective response [33]. Also of note is Viollon and Lavandier's identification of valence and arousal as the two main underlying factors in assessment of environmental quality [25], indicating strong possibility of a high correlation between SD pairs and the SAM.

2.3 Test Procedure

Each test subject is first presented with the pre-experiment statement and consent form, followed by a demographic

Figure 2. Test participant in the listening space.

questionnaire and a preview of the subjective assessment questionnaire they will use to rate each presented soundscape. This was to give them the opportunity to raise any questions they may have about the questions they will be answering, and to familiarise themselves with the test procedure. Following this they are lead into the listening space, as shown in Fig. 2.

Subjects are then presented with each of the soundscape recordings in random order over the 16-speaker surround-sound listening setup. After each recording has finished

they are given time to fill out a subjective assessment form for each one. The typical duration of the entire procedure was around 40 minutes.

All of the questionnaire forms were prepared for presentation online, with only the pre-experiment statement and consent form, and a sheet of the term definitions presented as a hard copy¹.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Correlation Analysis

In order to compare the results for each rating scale with one another, the results for each scale were first normalised for test subject by calculating z -scores [34]. The correlation of each rating scale with each other one was then calculated for each subject (according to Pearson's R [35]), and then the mean correlation across the subjects was calculated. This mean was then compared with the calculated critical r value, and then plotted according to its significance and whether the correlation found was positive or negative. This critical value is given by

$$r_{\text{Critical}} = \frac{\text{TINV}(1 - \frac{\alpha}{2}, \text{df})}{\sqrt{(\text{TINV}(1 - \frac{\alpha}{2}, \text{df}))^2 + \text{df}}} \quad (1)$$

where r_{Critical} is the minimum critical correlation value, TINV computes the inverse of the cumulative distribution function of the t -distribution, using the degrees of freedom df , and the critical probability value α [36]. For these results $\text{df} = 14$ (i.e. $n - 2$), and $\alpha = 0.05$, giving an r_{Critical} value of 0.4973 [36].

Figure 3 shows the results of this significance testing for each pair of rating scales. White square represent no significant correlation (the white squares with black crosses indicate where the correlation value is for a rating scale's correlation with itself i.e. $r = 1$). The red squares indicate positive correlation, and the blue squares indicate negative correlation. For the SD pairs the direction of the correlation is given where the second descriptor is positive, and the first descriptor is negative. For example, the negative correlation between Valence and the Quiet-Noisy SD pair indicates a significant correlation between increased Valence rating and Quiet-Noisy ratings closer to the Quiet end of that scale.

3.1.1 Uncorrelated Scales

There are several features of the collected data indicated by Figure 3 that merit discussion. One is that the Social-Unsocial, Informative-Meaningless, and Immersion scales are not correlated significantly with any rating scales. In the case of the Immersion scale this is a positive result, as it indicates that for a set of recordings all presented in the same format are similarly immersive independent of context.

¹ One test participant was presented with a pen-and-paper version of the survey instead, due to their lack of comfort in using the computerised version. This was considered to be suitable for inclusion after Bradley and Lang's findings of correlation values of 0.99, 0.94, and 0.79 for each dimension of the SAM (valence, arousal, and dominance respectively) compared between a pen-and-paper version and a computerised version [4].

This result for the Social-Unsocial and Informative-Meaningless scales is a reflection of some informal feedback from test participants indicating a perceived ambiguity in these two scales. In the case of Social-Unsocial there is a certain paradox present where an ostensibly sociable environment (e.g. Location 6 Albion St, Leeds) sounds overly busy and does not feel like an inviting place to take part in social activities: a fact evidenced by the different ratings for this scale for the two clips recorded at this location. Conversely, a quiet or empty soundscape (e.g. Location 1 Dalby Forest) may sound like an encouraging place for an activity to take place, even if the soundscape itself does not contain any social sounds.

A similar confusion is evident in the results for the Informative-Meaningless scale, as there is no explication of what constitutes 'true' meaning and information. For example, traffic noise conveys information regarding the rate and volume of passing cars present in the soundscape but is in many other ways meaningless. This maybe indicates a blurred boundary between the 'keynote' and 'signal' sounds as identified by Schafer [37]. Without a wider context (such as would be provided by a presented visual setting), it is not facile to identify which sounds provide a backdrop, and those sound which comprise the foreground of the soundscape (if indeed there are any such sounds present).

The Interesting-Boring and Varied-Monotonous scales (beyond their correlation with one another) are not correlated with any other scales, apart from Dislike-Like which is negatively correlated with Interesting-Boring. This indicates that the two scales are in effect synonymous making one of them redundant. The lack of significant correlation with any of the other scales is again evidence of rating scales that are relatively ambiguous, This is perhaps due to the dependence on an individuals other interests in determining how boring a soundscape is. For example a committed ornithologist might find the recording at location 1, a forest environment with many birds present, to be very interesting in a way that someone apathetic to birds might not. In this way these scales could be seen as 'overly subjective' where it is not just where a stimulus rates on a scale that is a subjective point, but where the meaning of the scale itself also varies between individuals.

3.1.2 SAM Results

Regarding the other SD pairs used in the experiment, Figure 3 indicates that the scales Quiet-Noisy, Comforting-Discomforting, Pleasant-Unpleasant, Harmonious-Dissonant, Soft-Rough, Rural-Urban, and Calming-Agitating are all similar correlated with one another and can therefore be considered as representing the same rating scale (with Dislike-Like representing the same scale again but with reversed polarity).

Almost all of these scales are also negatively correlated with Valence (apart from Dislike-Like with which, as one might expect, it is positively correlated). This fact evidences that the Valence dimension of the SAM is just as informative as several of the SD pairs, meriting its future use as a replacement subjective measure.

Another positive result is the lack of significant corre-

Figure 3. Plot showing the significant correlations between the rating scales used in the experiment. These values were calculated by taking an average of the correlation values between the rating scales for each participant, and then compared to the critical value for r described by the data.

lation between Valence and Arousal. The correlation of Arousal with the Quiet-Noisy and Tranquillity scales shows that the meaning of the Arousal scale has been correctly understood by the test participants, with the lack of significant correlation between Valence and Arousal indicating that the two scale are indeed measuring different elements of the subject experience, even if they can be indirectly related to one another due to their significant correlations with other rating scales. This justifies the future use of the Arousal dimension of the SAM in lieu of relevant SD pairs.

It is interesting to see in Figure 3 the significant correlation of Valence and Arousal with Dominance, as well as the correlation of Dominance with majority of the SD pairs. This is perhaps to be expected given Bradley and Lang’s previous findings with the Dominance dimension of the SAM. They found that for the IAPS and IADS dimension that the meaning of the Dominance scale could be confusing; when rating the dominance of a photograph of, for example, a mutilated corpse the question arises as to whether the Dominance should be rated from the perspective of the viewer or the subject of the photograph [4].

In this case of this experiment then, the significant correlation of the Dominance with other ratings scales indicates that whilst it is a scale that might not provide too much information beyond that given by the Valence and Arousal scales, it is at least explicit to participants what the Domi-

nance dimension means.

3.2 Circumplex Model of Affect

Another way of visualising the Valence and Arousal ratings for the soundscapes presented is to plot them as a Circumplex Model of Affect, a two-dimensional emotional space with arousal as one dimension and valence as another [5]. This is shown in Figure 4 where mean valence and arousal values for the set of clips have been (rescaled between ± 1) and plotted in 2D space.

The first thing apparent from Figure 4 is that the presented clips indicate a lack of spaces that are both valent and arousing. This leads to the question of whether there can be such a thing as a valent and arousing soundscape. This would require a busy soundscape with plenty of activity, but in a pleasant context (for the IAPS and IADS this has included examples such as erotica or a roller coaster). It remains to be seen, then, whether an example soundscape can be found that is both highly arousing and highly valent when presented in isolation, as the lack of visual context results essentially in increased aural arousal being equated with noise.

For these results then a pattern can be seen where increased arousal is associated primarily with the increased presence of traffic (as evidenced in Figure 4 by the differ-

Figure 4. A plot of the mean arousal and valence values for each clip on the ‘Circumplex Model of Affect’, identifying their positions in 2D emotional space. The numbers correspond to the 16 recording clips used in the experiment, where there were two clips for each recording location. As such clips 1 and 2 represent location 1, clips 3 and 4 represent location 2, and so on up to location 8 (clips 15 and 16).

ence between the position of clip 3 and 4). Both of these clips were recorded at location 2 within 10 minutes of one another. The only difference between them is the presence of a single car driving by in clip 3 that is not present in clip 4. Future work using the visual data recorded at these locations will illuminate whether the pleasant visual setting will change subjective experience of an environment.

Fig. 4 also shows how the recording locations used can be separated into three broad categories:

- **Relaxing environments:** e.g. locations 1 and 2 in the bottom-right quadrant of the figure. These locations are situated in a rural forest environment, and contain the highest proportion of natural/animal sounds, as well as representing the lowest recorded SPL levels.
- **Neutrally rated environments:** such as locations 3 and 8 that inhabit the middle sections of the figure. These environments included a mixture of rural and urban features, and further experimentation will show how the visual features present in each environment may change positions in emotional space.
- **Stressful environments:** such as locations 6 and 7 that are placed in the upper-left quadrant. These recordings contain the highest proportion of traffic noise and other mechanical sounds, as well as representing the highest recorded SPL levels.

4. CONCLUSION

This paper has shown the results of an experiment comparing the use of SD pairs and the SAM for soundscape preference ratings. It was hypothesised that a comparison of soundscape preference rating results between a set of SD pairs and the SAM will show the SAM to be a directly comparable and equally useful tool for the analysis of subjective soundscape experience.

The correlation analysis results, as detailed in Section 3.1 and summarised in Fig. 3, have shown support for this hypothesis as the valence and arousal dimensions of the SAM correlate with the chosen SD pairs in such a way that they can be considered to explain the test subjects’ responses to the data in a way that is just as meaningful as the SD pairs, but is less time consuming due to smaller number of rating scales. Dominance is shown to be of little use, which reflects findings from previous research and justifies abandoning its use in future experimentation. Feedback from test participants indicated that many felt the SAM was more intuitive to use than the SD pairs, which is borne out by the lack of significant correlation results for the Interesting-Boring, Social-Unsocial, and Informative-Meaningless rating scales.

The results shown in Section 3.2 indicate that the chosen recording locations do indeed cover a wide range of emotional ratings, but illuminate the lack of soundscape recordings that are both valent and arousing. It will be interesting to see whether the presentation of the recorded visual data alongside the soundscapes will change their perception and, accordingly, their positions in emotional space.

There are several further avenues of investigation to take in order to further explore the collected data. One is the analysis of biometric data collected alongside the subjective rating data examined in this paper, and the use of principal component analysis to further analyse the results presented here. The visual data recorded alongside the soundscape will also be presented to allow for the analysis of cross-modal perception. Another experiment has also been planned to compare SAM results with soundscape categorisation ratings assessing the recordings in terms of the three sound source groups identified in section 2.1.1.

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